

Fostering Open Knowledge Sharing for CubeSat Design through the SPACE4YOU Project

SPOKE 1 – Aerospace and sustainable mobility
Flagship Project – Space4You

CONFERENCE PAPER

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

25 – 27 SEPTEMBER 2024

FOSTERING OPEN KNOWLEDGE SHARING FOR CUBESAT DESIGN THROUGH THE SPACE4YOU PROJECT

Emanuela La Bella⁽¹⁾, Serena Campioli⁽¹⁾, Sabrina Corpino⁽¹⁾, Fabrizio Stesina⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾*Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (DIMEAS), Politecnico di Torino*

Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129, Torino, Italy

Email: emanuela.labella@polito.it, serena.campioli@polito.it, sabrina.corpino@polito.it, fabrizio.stesina@polito.it

INTRODUCTION

Concurrent Engineering is a systematic approach to integrated product development aiming to reduce time to mission design and development costs, while increasing the systems development quality, by carrying out tasks in parallel with a quasi near-real-time teamwork. To effectively implement a design approach, it is important to complement it with suitable tools and standardized procedures that can improve the design process and facilitate cooperation among team members and scientific communities' collaboration.

In this context, the paper emphasizes the significance of knowledge sharing to foster coordination within a unique framework that can provide solutions to increase the capabilities and outcomes of small satellite missions [1]. In addition, the paper presents the implementation of knowledge sharing through the SPACE4YOU (SPace Activities and CompEtences for induStrY bOost in bUusiness) flagship project, which is part of Spoke 1 – Industry 4.0 for sustainable mobility and aerospace – of the innovation ecosystem NODES – Nord-Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile (Digital and Sustainable North-Western Italy) – involving the North-Western Italian regions of Piemonte, Valle d'Aosta and the bordering provinces of Lombardia. A tangible outcome of the project is the creation of a central knowledge portal, named *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal*, which consists of an accessible database of skills and expertise available in the aerospace research ecosystem. It serves as an open-source web repository for collective resources, including techniques, methodologies, models, procedures, and tools for designing, simulating, developing, and testing new space systems. The portal promotes collaboration, open knowledge exchange, and technology transfer between academia, large companies, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), accelerators, and incubators within the space ecosystem, ensuring open access to the entire ecosystem.

First, Knowledge Management (KM) strategies and the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal* architecture are introduced, followed by an in-depth look at one of the contributions to knowledge sharing that focuses on concurrent engineering in the space field. It consists of the development of open-source materials, such as methodologies and digital tools, which play a key role in enhancing the small satellite mission and service design. These tools, tailored for CubeSats preliminary design, are a *Small-Satellite System Design (S3D) Tool*, which consists of Microsoft Excel spreadsheets dedicated to the main disciplines of a preliminary design phase, allowing to perform the sizing and evaluation of the spacecraft subsystems budgets, and a comprehensive *CubeSat Technologies Database (CUTE-DB)*, providing immediate access to specifications and performance data of commercially available components, supporting not only the component selection but also ensuring that CubeSat projects are based on current technological realities, and that design processes are efficient. While the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal* is at a prototype level, both *S3D Tool* and *CUTE-DB* have been implemented and tested in concurrent design sessions, but they are not yet publicly available through the portal.

The critical role of open knowledge sharing in fostering a collaborative and efficient space sector is underlined. The open-source approach of the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal* demonstrates the potential of publicly available resources to accelerate innovation, promote best practices, facilitate knowledge transfer between academia and industry, and enable aerospace ecosystem actors to leverage collective expertise in space systems design. The knowledge portal is designed to be continuously enriched by all entities, including universities and research institutions, which, as part of the academia, have the unique responsibility of contributing their valuable mission-derived knowledge to the public domain. This not only encourages collaboration but also ensures that lessons learned are not lost, paving the way for a future of continuous improvement in space exploration and development. Finally, as a result of both the implementation of concurrent design tools during several concurrent sessions and the try-out of the beta version of the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal*, some recommendations on KM strategy and knowledge portal maintenance are outlined.

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Distinguishing between data, information, and knowledge is essential: if, on one hand, data refers to raw events without any inherent meaning, on the other hand, information adds meaning to data through contextual relationships. Finally, knowledge builds upon information by providing actionable insights based on experience and understanding [2]. According to [3], it is possible to differentiate between tacit and explicit knowledge. *Tacit knowledge* pertains to individuals' personal skills, background, and experiential learning, making it challenging to formalize. In contrast, *explicit knowledge* is readily articulated, transmitted, and documented. Therefore, Knowledge Management (KM) can be defined as “a process that helps organizations find, select, organize, disseminate, and transfer important information and expertise necessary for activities such as problem-solving, dynamic learning, strategic planning and decision making” [4].

Knowledge strategy includes planning for future knowledge needs and bridging the gaps between existing and required knowledge. It involves identifying knowledge resources and defining the necessary knowledge for the organization. Various KM strategies have been proposed, including knowledge creation, knowledge transfer, knowledge strategy as business strategy, etc [5] [6]. Even if each strategy has its advantages and disadvantages, knowledge creation can be considered as a prerequisite for the others: different models have been developed for the knowledge creation process. A particularly interesting one is the SECI (Socialization, Externalization, Combination, Internalization) model [7], which represents a dynamic interaction between tacit and explicit knowledge in a spiral process. This interaction occurs among individuals, groups, and organizations, leading to the enhancement of knowledge.

Fig. 1. SECI Process [7]

As shown in Fig. 1, knowledge creation is a spiral, where the interaction between the two types of knowledge is enhanced through the four modes of knowledge conversion. As the spiral progresses through ontological levels, it expands in scale: knowledge generated through the SECI process can initiate a new spiral of knowledge creation, extending horizontally and vertically across organizations. This interactive spiral process occurs both within and between organizations; hence, knowledge extends beyond organizational perimeters, and knowledge from different organizations interacts to generate new knowledge. Through dynamic interaction, knowledge generated within the organization can stimulate the activation of knowledge held by external entities such as users, affiliated companies, universities, or suppliers.

The implementation of a KM strategy as part of SPACE4YOU seeks to achieve two strategic goals. The first is to establish (and continuously foster) a *knowledge culture* within the North-Western Italian region entities, as part of NODES project, and the second is to enhance the *operational efficiency*, aiming at a more efficient design and implementation of space projects. Therefore, the objectives of the SPACE4YOU Knowledge Management strategy are: (OBJ1) Promote and facilitate knowledge sharing to enhance collaboration and synergies among the different actors; (OBJ2) Capture, develop, and maintain knowledge from various space missions and projects to enhance the effectiveness of current and future ones, reducing risks, costs and preventing loss of expertise; (OBJ3) Establish methods and tools to discover, organize and share knowledge within the regional entities themselves to boost the North-West Italian space ecosystem.

The main outcome in addressing these objectives is the implementation of the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal*, a database of the competencies and skills available in the aerospace research ecosystem, accessible through a public web interface, collecting the research areas and reference contact persons. It will be deployed starting from the competencies of the partners of the flagship project, but it is intended as a living database, that will be enriched along the project and maintained, as a reference point for a global picture of the technical competencies of the Space research in the area. In the knowledge portal, among the different resources available, a *CubeSat Technologies Database (CUTE-DB)* is

published forming a collection of information on CubeSat systems, subsystems, and components currently available on the market, as part of the knowledge-sharing philosophy, with a low-level perspective.

KNOWLEDGE PORTAL

SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal is currently under development, and it has not been released to the public yet. However, a preliminary web interface has been developed to be tested internally before the official publication. The knowledge portal architecture, shown in Fig. 2, consists of three main blocks: the *About* one in which it is possible to find out about the team that is contributing to the research, on the *Team* page, and the success stories relating to the different research topics, on the *Case Studies* page; the *Research Areas* block gives to the user an overview of the macro-areas covered within the project; finally, the *Tools* block in which all the tools developed and available are accessible.

SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal Architecture

Fig. 2. SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal Architecture

Expanding on the Research Areas, those involved are *Design*, *Development*, *Operations*, and *Exploitation*. Each macro-area expands in turn into specific research topics, such as the *Concurrent & Virtual Design*, subject of this work. This shows the versatility of the knowledge portal, grouping many topics into a unique virtual place. The preliminary architecture presented here is not intended to be frozen and definitive, as it will always be possible to add specific research topics, as well as macro areas, thus expanding the knowledge portal.

Concurrent Design Tools

As part of the *Design* research area, in the *Concurrent & Virtual Design* page of the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal* (Fig. 3), both methodologies and tools are made available for users to implement effective strategies for space missions and systems design, with a focus on the CubeSat class of satellite.

Fig. 3. Example of *Concurrent & Virtual Design* page (not official, nor released, only for visualization purposes)

The focus is on the Concurrent Engineering approach, a product development approach where tasks are performed simultaneously, and modern design tools are employed to reduce time-to-market at a lower cost with higher quality. This methodology is particularly suitable for the phase 0/A [8] design of space missions and systems. Therefore, the *Small-*

Satellite System Design (S3D) Tool is provided to support different users, including companies that may not be currently involved in the space sector but aim either to enter this ecosystem or apply its methodologies to their product development. Developed at Politecnico di Torino by the STAR (Systems and Technologies for Aerospace Research) team, *S3D Tool* is composed of a set of Calculation Sheets in Microsoft Excel, as reported in Fig. 4, covering several disciplines such as Attitude Determination and Control Systems (ADCS), Communication Systems (CommSys), Electrical Power Systems (EPS), Propulsion Systems, Thermal Systems, Risks, and Costs. To facilitate communication and information management, there is a central repository, named *Central Data Exchange System* as in Fig. 4, still developed in Excel. This repository is linked to the other workbooks and allows for both automated and manual data input. Its purpose is to ensure that up-to-date information and data are shared across different disciplines and levels (mission, system, subsystem, component) while verifying that all disciplines operate on the same assumptions. Additionally, in the central repository, a quick mass and volume budget is automatically computed.

Fig. 4. S3D Tool

The *S3D Tool* is complemented by the *CubeSat Technologies Database (CUTE-DB)*, a comprehensive open-source database that provides immediate access to specifications and performance data of commercially available components. This not only supports component selection but also ensures designs are grounded in current technological realities, facilitating efficient design processes. Open-source knowledge databases store information and are shared with users for free, allowing them to create a system based on their needs and requirements. The first sharable version of the *CUTE-DB* is an Excel-based database, covering several technologies such as CubeSat deployers, Structures, Command and Data Handling (C&DH) systems, Electric Propulsion Systems (EPS), Attitude Determination & Control Systems (ADCS), Communication Systems (CommSys), Propulsion Systems, Navigation Systems, Optical payloads, Docking Systems, Mechanisms, and Platforms. Their properties and relationships with other technologies are highlighted in the database and it represents a picture of what is currently available in the market. The database structure is kept consistent throughout the different sheets related to the different disciplines, covering the following areas: (i) Item description (name, type, description, reference links); (ii) Developer details (company name, country of origin); (iii) Physical properties (dimensions, mass, physical interfaces, etc.); (iv) Functional properties (technology-dependent); (v) Environmental properties (survival temperatures, operational properties, radiation tolerance, etc.); (vi) Power properties (supply current, nominal power, peak power, voltage supply, electrical interfaces, etc.); (vii) Flight Heritage (Technology Readiness Level, Heritage); (viii) Price (when available). *CUTE-DB* has been populated within the NODES project activities by the STAR team, using several sources including [9], [10], [11] and it is currently updated to June 2024. An overview of the contents of the *CUTE-DB* is shown in Fig. 5, with a focus on solar cell technologies to highlight the sheet layout.

Fig. 5. CUTE - DB

Once the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal* is officially released to the public, the database will be accessible to the users, and they will be encouraged to complement the different parts of the database through a form available on the web page. Periodically, the different inputs will be collected, evaluated, and eventually integrated for a new release of *CUTE-DB*. The frequency of this review is under evaluation, as different factors need to be taken into account, such as the available funding and the research group responsible, as well as the time needed for careful data validation.

CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

Incorporating a Knowledge Management (KM) strategy for *SPACE4YOU* has been an essential measure in fostering a culture of knowledge sharing and improving the operational efficacy of space projects, in the North-Western Italian region as part of *NODES* objectives.

At this stage of the project, all the relevant materials, procedures, and tools are ready to be published as they have been tested on several occasions. For instance, the *S3D Tool* with *CUTE-DB* has been employed during many concurrent studies at Politecnico di Torino [12], allowing for iteration in the tool itself thanks to the lessons learned and the feedback received by the participants in the sessions. The beta version of the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal* has been tested internally and the official portal is soon to be released to the public. The first release will be crucial to fix eventual bugs and gather feedback from early users to enhance the user experience, as well as gain a deeper understanding and meet the needs of the users.

Moreover, the open-source approach of the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal*, including tools like *S3D* and *CUTE-DB*, holds great potential to accelerate the innovation process of the main space actors, by providing readily accessible resources and best practices. The knowledge transfer is facilitated, ensuring a closer collaboration on space systems design between academic/research institutions and industries. The collective expertise of the entire space ecosystem can also be exploited by stakeholders, tapping into it through the portal. Lastly, faster and lower-cost development cycles of the design process for small satellite missions are streamlined by standardized procedures and tools like *S3D*, leading to enhanced operational efficiency.

Recommendations

The results of the *S3D* and *CUTE-DB* implementation in concurrent studies and the try-out of the beta *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal* allowed to draw the following recommendations.

One of the crucial recommendations is to establish a robust process for the continuous validation and updating of knowledge repositories. This involves defining clear roles and responsibilities for data collection, evaluation, and integration. Implementing automated tools where possible is also recommended, in order to streamline data entry and validation, thus decreasing the manual workload and potential for errors. Additionally, scheduling periodic evaluations

to assess the effectiveness of the KM strategy and making necessary adjustments based on user feedback and technological advancements is important.

User engagement should be encouraged, regularly seeking feedback to understand user needs and subsequently improve the system. Furthermore, conducting workshops and training sessions to familiarize users with the portal's functionalities and the significance of their contributions could be a way to foster user engagement.

Finally, the promotion of a knowledge-sharing culture is deemed fundamental, as recognizing and rewarding contributions to the *SPACE4YOU Knowledge Portal*, highlighting success stories and case studies, and fostering collaboration among different actors play a crucial role in promoting a culture of knowledge sharing and innovation. This can be achieved through an effective outreach campaign including not only online platforms and social media but also live events in the North-West Italian territory addressing different age groups and different professionals.

By implementing the presented recommendations, the SPACE4YOU project can establish a solid and sustainable KM strategy, providing the space sector with a valuable resource for sharing knowledge and improving operational efficiency in space missions design and beyond, initially to the North-West Italian regions and, after a consolidation of the portal, to academia, industry and agencies worldwide.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is part of the project NODES – Spoke 1 – Aerospace and Sustainable Mobility. The authors would like to acknowledge the NODES ecosystem for the support and the funding received from the MUR-M4C2 1.5 of PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036.

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